

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol by N-Chloro-3-methyl-2, 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone in Acid Medium

K. GANAPATHY* AND B. VIJAYAN

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 101

Manuscript received 6 March 1978, accepted 22 July 1978

The kinetic measurements of the oxidation of allyl alcohol have been made in 50% aqueous ethanol. The oxidation reaction is first order with respect to the oxidant and zero order with respect to the substrate. The rate is found to increase with increase in $[H^+]$ as well as $[Cl^-]$. Effect of neutral salt viz. NaClO, shows the reaction to exhibit a negative salt effect. The energy of activation and entropy of activation have been found to be 21.54 k cal mol⁻¹ and -6.21 e.u. respectively.

DURING our studies on the oxidation of a substituted piperidone with chloramine-T, we obtained a new compound which was found to be N-chloro-3-methyl-2, 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone. Surprisingly this was found to behave in a manner similar to N-chlorosuccinimide and hence we employed this as the oxidant for the oxidation of allyl alcohol in the present study.

The oxidation of allyl alcohol has been studied by several workers¹⁻³. Jones and Waters point out that allyl and crotonyl alcohols are oxidised by vanadium(V) more easily than their saturated analogues, due to the formation of mesomeric intermediates. Chloramine-T was employed as the oxidant by Mahadevappa and Naidu⁴.

Experimental

N-Chloro-3-methyl-2, 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone(I) was prepared by passing chlorine through the solution of 3-methyl-2, 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone hydrochloride in 75% ethanol-water mixture for about 30 minutes. On dilution with excess amount of water, the oxidised material was thrown out which on recrystallization from ethanol yielded colourless crystals, m.p. 190-191°(d) (Found: C, 72.25; H, 6.27; N, 4.45%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈ClNO: C, 72.13; H, 6.01; N, 4.67%).

E Merck allyl alcohol was distilled and the fraction collected at 97° was used. Analar perchloric acid, potassium chloride and sodium perchlorate were used as such. All kinetic measurements were carried out in 50% ethanol-water mixture(V/V) unless otherwise stated. The kinetic measurements were made by estimating the aliquot portions of reaction mixtures for the oxidant iodometrically using starch as indicator.

Stoichiometry

Reaction mixtures containing an excess of the oxidant over allyl alcohol were kept at room

temperature in presence of hydrochloric acid (0.05 M) for 24 hours. Estimation of the unchanged oxidant showed that one mole of allyl alcohol consumed one mole of the oxidant.

The product, acraldehyde, was identified polarographically.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of allyl alcohol by N-chloro-3-methyl-2, 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. When allyl alcohol was in large excess, plots of $\log(a-x)$ against time were found to be linear (Fig 1). The pseudo-first order constants in the oxidant calculated at different initial concentrations of the reactants (Table 1) were found to be independent of the substrate concentration. Hence it is concluded that the reaction is first order with respect to the oxidant and zero order in allyl alcohol.

Effect of Variation of Acid Concentration: The kinetics of the reaction was studied with different concentrations of hydrogen ion keeping the concentrations of the oxidant and allyl alcohol constant.

Fig. 1. First order plots at 30° for the reaction of allyl alcohol with the oxidant.

[H⁺]=2.23 × 10⁻³ M; [Cl⁻]=5.0 × 10⁻² M; [Allyl alcohol]-excess

[Oxidant]
 A, 0.75 × 10⁻³ M;
 B, 1.00 × 10⁻³ M;
 C, 1.25 × 10⁻³ M.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION

[Oxidant]—0.001M, [H⁺]-0.025M, [Cl⁻]-0.05M,
 Temperature 30° ± 0.1°

10 ³ [allyl alcohol] M	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
1.0	2.15
2.0	2.12
3.0	2.14
4.0	2.17

The rate increased linearly with the increase in hydrogen ion concentration. The rate constant divided by hydrogen ion concentration gave a constant value (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DEPENDANCE OF RATE ON ACID

[Oxidant]—0.001M, [Cl⁻]-0.05M, [allyl alcohol]-excess,
 Temperature 30° ± 0.1°

[H ⁺] × 10 ³ M	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	{ $\frac{k}{[H^+]}$ } × 10 ³ l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1.78	1.52	8.53
2.23	1.95	8.75
2.67	2.17	8.12
3.12	2.69	8.62
3.57	3.06	8.58

Effect of Chloride Ion Concentration: In the absence of chloride ion the reaction was very slow. The rate constants were measured at different concentrations of chloride ion and found to increase

with increase of chloride ion concentration. A plot of log k against log [Cl⁻] gave a straight line.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING CHLORIDE ION CONCENTRATION

[Oxidant]—0.001M, [H⁺]-0.0223M, [allyl alcohol]-excess,
 Temperature 30° ± 0.1°

[Cl ⁻] × 10 ² M	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	$\frac{k}{[Cl^-]} \times 10^3$ l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
2.5	0.96	3.80
5.0	1.95	3.86
6.25	2.32	3.70
7.5	2.55	3.46
1.0	3.19	3.20

Effect of Ionic Strength: The ionic strength of the reaction medium was varied by adding sodium perchlorate. The rate decreased with increase of ionic strength (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH

[Oxidant]—0.001M, [HCl] 0.0518M, [allyl alcohol]-excess,
 Temperature 30° ± 0.1°, solvent—60% ethanol-water mixture

Ionic strength	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.05	8.67
0.10	6.92
0.15	6.33
0.20	6.18
0.25	5.63

Effect of Dielectric Constant of the Medium: The decrease of dielectric constant of the reaction medium (due to increase of the percentage of ethanol in the reaction mixture) increased the rate of the reaction (Table 5). When the percentage of ethanol was plotted against rate constant a straight line was obtained.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM

[Oxidant]—0.001M, [H⁺]-0.025M, [Cl⁻] 0.05M,
 [allyl alcohol]-excess, Temperature 30° ± 0.1°

Percentage of ethanol	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
45	1.71
50	2.19
55	2.67
60	3.00
65	3.71

Effect of Temperature: Rate constants were measured at different temperatures (30-42.5°). The energy and entropy of activation have been found to be 21.54 k cal mol⁻¹ and -6.21 e.u. respectively.

Hughes and Ingold⁵ during the study of Orton rearrangement of N-haloacetanilides, suggested that the rate determining reaction takes place between chloride ion and the protonated N-haloamide. Taking into account all the data presented so far, the following-mechanism is proposed for the oxidation reaction.

$$\text{Rate of the reaction} = k_1 [\text{>N}^+\text{HCl}] [\text{Cl}^-]$$

$$\text{where } [\text{>N}^+\text{HCl}] = K [\text{>N-Cl}] [\text{H}^+]$$

$$\text{Rate of the reaction} = Kk_1 [\text{>N-Cl}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]$$

$$\frac{-d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{>N-Cl}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]$$

The second step viz. the reaction between the protonated N-halopiperidone and the chloride ion is the rate determining one. This is substantiated by the negative salt effect and the increase in the rate noted due to decrease in the dielectric constant of the solution. The free chlorine formed by the step (2) reacts with allyl alcohol at a faster rate which shows the zero order dependence of the reaction with respect to allyl alcohol.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.V.) is thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. Selvavinayakam, CIBA-Geigy, Bombay for providing micro-analysis data.

References

1. H. LAND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2129.
2. J. R. JONES and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2068.
3. B. SETHURAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, 35, 254.
4. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and H. M. K. NAIDU, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 1203.
5. E. D. HUGHES and C. K. INGOLD, *Q. Rev. (Lond.)*, 1952, 6, 34.